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Title The All-inclusive Tourism system
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Abstract Small island developing States
have enjoyed significant economic
development in recent years due,
in most cases, to rising numbers
of tourist visitors. In this paper,
we present an analysis of tourism
development in Cape Verde during
the period 2004-2013 which clearly
shows that the socioeconomic development
of the country has advanced in
parallel with increasing arrivals
of tourists. In particular, we
examine the tourist resort island
of Sal, and present the results
of a field study focused on tourists
visiting the island under an all-inclusive
system. The main results obtained
by reflect these visitors hi
of satisfaction, especially with
respect to the beaches and the
public safety. As an aspect to
be improved, the study highlights
the need to strengthen the interaction
between visitors and the local
community.

Keywords Satisfaction; Cluster Analysis;
Resorts; Economics Data; Diaspora;
SIDS.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The advent of tourism in certain resort areas has led to sharply rising socio-economic development, sometimes contributing to a change in the local economic structure. Thus, in certain States, as a result of the tourism boom the model of economic production has undergone a radical change. An example of this can be seen in Cape Verde, a country whose economy was characterised, until 15 or 20 years ago, by a predominance of the primary sector and an economy based on cooperation aid from developed countries and by remittances from emigrants. However, in 2007 the World Bank declared Cape Verde a middle-income country. This change was due to the impact of diverse variables, some of a political nature, such as a well-consolidated democratic political system, based on the rule of law, together with excellent legal security and also the country's international outlook, based on very close trade relations with the European Union; other variables were of a commercial nature, and reflected a change in the business model, with a greater focus on the tourism sector and, therefore, on construction.

Much research has been conducted into tourism in island nations. One reason for this is that islands, after historic cities, are the most popular destinations for tourists (Correia, Butler & Oliveira, 2008). A further consideration is that it is necessary to encourage an appropriate and sustainable form of tourism, to benefit both the local population and their visitors (Cusick, 2009) whereby it is necessary to analyse the relationship among the different stakeholders involved in tourism sector (Sánchez-Cañizares, Castillo Canalejo & Núñez Tabales, 2015). However, the question of tourism in island destinations cannot be analysed as a single issue, because there are considerable differences among islands, regarding size, location, climate, etc. Among island states are those termed Small Island Developing States (SIDS), defined as territories that are no larger than 5000 km² and which have no more than two million inhabitants. These countries are economically very vulnerable for reasons

including lack of resources, insularity, low birth rate and very small domestic markets (Sharpley & Ussi, 2014). In consequence, there is a need to diversify their economy, for example, by promoting medical tourism (Connell, 2013).

Cape Verde is one of the SIDS where the development of tourism has taken two different routes. In the first of these, the islands of Sal and Boa Vista are characterised by a commitment to large-scale resorts, financed by European capital, where tourists stay in hotels on an all-inclusive basis. In addition, there are large numbers of second homes, mainly owned by Europeans. This type of tourism began on the island of Sal and has recently been introduced into the island of Boa Vista, showing direct impacts on the host community attitude towards tourism development (Castillo-Canalejo, Núñez Tabales & Sánchez Cañizares, 2016). As we discuss below, the tourism data clearly reflect the emergence of Boa Vista in all-inclusive tourism. The second type of tourism development is that carried out in the other islands that make up Cape Verde, and is based on the construction and rehabilitation of small hotels; this activity is generally financed by remittances from emigrants and managed by the local community. Even in the nation's capital, Praia, on the island of Santiago, as well as two large hotels belonging to major European hotel chains, there are many small hotels.

The aim of this paper is twofold: on the one hand, to present the evolution of tourism in Cape Verde in general and on the island of Sal in particular during the past decade (from 2004-2013) to demonstrate the direct relationship between tourism and economic change in the country. And on the other hand, to present and discuss the results of a field study carried out on the island of Sal, focused on tourists staying at an all-inclusive resort, to determine their socio-demographic profile and their opinions and assessments of the all-inclusive system. To achieve these two objectives, the article is structured as follows. After this introduction, we review the literature concerning the All Inclusive System (AIS); section three then describes the geographic aspects of the study area; section four presents the methodology

used, and section five, the study results. Finally, the main conclusions drawn are summarised and the bibliographic references listed.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The all-inclusive system originated in “holiday camps” in Great Britain during the 1930s, and was subsequently developed in the resorts of the Club Méditerranée in the 1950s (Issa & Jayawardena, 2003). But the large-scale introduction of the system took place in the Caribbean, beginning with Jamaica, in the 1970s, where the image of sun and sand was combined with that of the traditional hospitality of the region (Chambers & Airey, 2001; Issa & Jayawardena, 2003; Ayik, Benetatos & Evagelou, 2013). Currently, the AIS is well established in the Caribbean, in various Mediterranean countries, on both European and African shores, and in certain areas of Africa and Southeast Asia (primarily Indonesia and Thailand) (González Herrera & Palafox Muñoz, 2007). By country of origin, these tourists mainly come from Europe and North America (Anderson, 2010), and have a middle-income level (Ayik et al., 2013). In recent years, the AIS concept has been extended from coastal zones to be applied on cruises, too (Issa & Jayawardena, 2003) and via tour packages (Wong & Kwong, 2004).

The AIS is an important innovation, as a product aimed at the international tourism market, based above all on minimising monetary transactions during tourists’ stay. The basic features of this system are the inclusion in the final price (usually paid in the tourists’ country of origin) of the cost of accommodation, meals, drinks and a range of complementary tourist services (Wong & Kwong, 2004; González Herrera & Palafox Muñoz, 2007). The system is applied mainly in coastal locations (Anderson, 2010). It is also commonly adopted in resorts where levels of public safety are low and in places lacking complementary extra-hotel attractions, especially as regards meals, leisure facilities and night life (González Herrera &

Palafox Muñoz, 2007), although in recent years the AIS has spread to other regions where in fact there is a wide range of complementary attractions. This is the case, for example, in certain parts of Spain and Portugal, and this has provoked considerable debate about the positive and negative effects of this system in such areas.

Among its positive effects, the AIS can increase the revenue obtained by tour operators and travel agents, create reasonably-priced travel opportunities for tourists, raise occupancy rates at resorts, introduce other types of product and simplify relations between hotels and their guests (Alegre & Pou, 2006; Özdemir, Çizel & Çizel, 2012). Negative outcomes include a possible decline in the quality of the tourism product, reduced staff motivation, a lack of interaction between tourists, mainly foreigners, and the local community (Çiftçi, Düzakin & Önal, 2007; Ozdemir et al., 2012; Castillo-Canalejo, Núñez-Tabales, Cerezo-López & Fuentes- García, 2015) and the fact that this system is not suitable for small hotels, calling for a minimum of about 150 rooms (Anderson, 2010). According to Wong and Kwong (2004), the AIS is positive and quite safe for tourists travelling from countries with different cultures, who know the type of resort they will find at their destination; however, they tend to be dissatisfied with their scant opportunity to experience other cultures in this type of holiday, due to the little or no interaction with the local community. Furthermore, the system can also be unsuitable for people with special dietary requirements (Condratov, 2014).

The AIS is, above all, a package holiday system, and should be defined as such (Alegre & Pou, 2006). It produces a major change in the tourist facilities offered at the destination (Alegre & Pou, 2006), mostly due to the almost complete disappearance of the catering sector as a result of a change in the flow of services offered at the destination, with the hotel appropriating an important part of this flow. Accordingly, a crucial factor to tourists' satisfaction is the quality of the hotel itself, including the cuisine provided and the quality of the drinks served at no extra charge in the hotel (Çiftçi et al., 2007; Ayik et al., 2013). On the

other hand, aspects of the area such as its culture, natural values and history are not considered as significant in determining tourists' choice of holiday destination (Ayik et al., 2013).

The AIS has become consolidated in many locations for various reasons: consumers know exactly what they will pay, before starting their holiday (Çizel, Çizel, Sarvan & Ozdemir, 2013); the important role played by travel intermediaries in promoting this system (Çizel et al., 2013); and the fact that this type of product accurately targets various categories of customers, such as couples, families, young people or pensioners (Çiftçi et al., 2007). In addition, this system presents an opportunity for tourism development in developing countries (Çizel et al., 2013), although one of the key aspects that needs to be analysed and discussed is that of the relationship between the resorts and local businesses supplying tourist-oriented goods and services (Anderson, 2010; Ribeiro, Valle & Silva, 2013), to determine the cash flows that would ultimately remain in the local economy. Similarly, it is necessary to analyse the geographical setting where these resorts are built and their relationships with the national governments, like for example, in questions related to the tax payments (Ambrosie, 2015).

Studies have been conducted into the application of the AIS in Spain (Alegre & Pou, 2006; Anderson, 2012), Romania (Condratov, 2014), Turkey (Ayik et al., 2013; Özdemir et al., 2012), Jamaica (Smith & Spencer, 2011), Dominican Republic (Moreno Gil, Celis Sosa & Aguiar Quintana, 2002), other Caribbean countries (Chamber & Airey, 2001), Malta (Chapman & Speake, 2011) and Mexico (González Herrera & Palafox Muñoz, 2007).

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE GEOGRAPHIC AREA

The Republic of Cape Verde is located in the Atlantic Ocean. It is composed of ten islands (nine inhabited and one uninhabited) that together comprise a total area of 4,033 square kilometres (Figure 1). Cape Verde was part of Portugal until its independence in 1975.

This African country is one where socio-economic development and democracy have become a reality thanks to its political stability, based on the alternation of two major political parties with a structure similar to that of European parties, and to the legal security enjoyed by foreign investors. Cape Verde is heavily influenced by European countries, especially Portugal. In 2007, a preferential agreement was signed with the European Union to strengthen trade relations and to enable access to European capital. Consequently, most hotel and construction investments on the islands of Sal and Boa Vista have been made with European capital, mainly Portuguese, Spanish, British and Italian. The total population of the country, according to the 2010 census (National Statistics Institute of Cape Verde, 2011) is 491,875 people, of whom 25,765 (5.24%) live on the island of Sal.

SEE FIGURE 1

This paper is focused on the island of Sal, traditionally the most popular destination for tourists in Cape Verde. It has an area of 216 square kilometres and a population of just over 25,000 people. The island, and its main town, Santa Maria, are characterised by the development of tourism based on the resort concept, but residential tourism has also spurred the construction of many developments. Until November 2005, the country's only international airport was located on the island of Sal, reflecting its important strategic situation. This island is specialised in sun and beach tourism, complemented by facilities for water sports, thanks to its excellent climate. The main strengths of this island are its road infrastructure, the strategic importance of the airport and the quality of the resorts, all of which are four and five-star rated. Its major areas for improvement include the need to strengthen basic public infrastructure such as healthcare services and sanitation, the inadequate supply of skilled labour for the tourism market and the practically complete absence of a commercial relationship between local fish suppliers (fishing is one of the basic activities of the island) and the hotels belonging to foreign chains, because the island has no

production processes to certify the quality and fitness of seafood for human consumption; accordingly, the fish cannot be acquired by these chains, which insist on the application of European standards (López-Guzmán, Borges, Hernández-Merino & Cerezo, 2013).

TABLE 1

Table 1 shows that GDP has increased significantly over the years in question, although, as noted above, it also shows that the economic crisis in Europe has had a major impact on the country. Another interesting finding is that tourism revenues have risen quite significantly while remittances have remained virtually flat. Together with these economic indicators, and from data supplied by the Central Bank of Cape Verde (2014), we can also describe the present state of the country's economy (in 2013). Thus, GDP at market prices was €1,487 million, GDP per capita was about €2,900, tourism accounted for 49% of the exports of goods and services, and foreign direct investment (FDI) related to tourism and associated real estate activity represented 71% of all FDI. As a very significant social indicator, let us highlight the literacy rate, which in Cape Verde is currently 82.8%.

Focusing on the tourism sector, the data in Table 2 show, for the period 2004-2013, the number of visitors and overnight stays both for the whole country and for the island of Sal alone. In the columns corresponding to the island of Sal, the figure in brackets reflects the percentage with respect to the value for the whole country.

SEE TABLE 2

According to Table 2, in the last decade the number of visitors has increased by nearly 300%, and that of overnight stays by 397%. Taking into account that the population of the country is about 500,000, this means that the number of tourists arriving each year exceeds the total population of the country.

With regard to the island of Sal, Table 2 shows that the number of tourists has risen by 160% and that of overnight stays by 216%, although the island's relative share of this market

has fallen significantly. The reason for this relative decline is, as noted above, the growing importance of the island of Boa Vista for this type of visitor.

With regard to supply, Table 3 shows the changes that have taken place in the numbers of hotels, bedrooms, beds and staff employed in Cape Verde during the period 2004-2013.

SEE TABLE 3

Table 3 shows that in the time period studied, there was a significant increase in the number of bedrooms (287%) and staff employed (266%), in response to rising numbers of visitors. In the same period, the ratio of the number of hotel bedrooms available to the number of staff employed rose from 1.45 rooms/employee in 2004 to 1.57 rooms/employee in 2013. A similar pattern can be observed with regard to the ratio of overnight stays to the number of staff employed, which rose from 399.59 in 2004 to 597.06 in 2013.

The supply of tourism infrastructure in the island of Sal, during the period 2004-2013, is shown in Table 4 (in brackets, the percentage with respect to the value for Cape Verde as a whole).

SEE TABLE 4

Table 4 highlights the increase in the absolute number of rooms (223%) and in staff employed (197%), although, as in the case of tourist demand, the relative percentages for Sal with respect to the country as a whole have fallen, due, once again, to the sharp rise in this respect in the island of Boa Vista. In the island of Sal there were seven resorts in 2013 offering more than 3000 rooms. Subsequently, more than the 80% of the total available rooms in this island in 2013 belong to this lodging typology. On the other hand, all these resorts had 4 or 5 stars category.

The ratio between the number of hotel rooms and the number of staff employed rose from 1.36 bedrooms/employee on the island of Sal in 2004 to 1.55 bedrooms/employee in

2013. The corresponding ratio for overnight stays per employee increased from 547.72 in 2004 to 600.72 in 2013.

4. METHODOLOGY

The research was based on a field study conducted to determine the sociodemographic profile of visitors to resorts in the island of Sal, in Cape Verde, and their evaluation of these resorts and the facilities offered.

The structure of the survey used was based on various previous studies (Kozak, 2002; Moreno Gil et al., 2002; Çiftçi et al., 2007; Anderson, 2012; Özdemir et al., 2012) and addressed four basic issues: the sociodemographic profile of the tourists, their evaluation of the resort where they were staying, the type of visit made and their opinion of the all-inclusive system.

The field study, based on surveys, was carried out from April to June 2014, in the departure lounge of the international airport on the island of Sal, as the tourists were leaving the island to return home. Surveys were only obtained from tourists who responded affirmatively to the prior question of whether their stay on the island had been at a resort in the AIS mode. The participants completed the survey alone, with no interference, although the interviewers were present to assist if any difficulty was encountered. The survey was distributed in four languages (English, Portuguese, French and German) and was completely anonymous. Previously, a pre-test of 30 surveys was conducted to detect possible bias or mistake. A total of 516 completed questionnaires were obtained.

The items used in the survey corresponded to indicators and measures that have been proposed to enable a useful analysis to be made of the data obtained. Thus, a mixture of technical questions was asked, in which a 5-point Likert scale was used to assess visitors' opinions, together with other questions calling for yes/no answers and both closed and open

questions in response to which the tourists were invited to comment on their all-inclusive experience. In total, 207,691 people visited the island of Sal in 2013. No official data are available on the numbers of tourists visiting Sal in the AIS mode. With this target population, the sampling error of the study was $\pm 4.31\%$. The reliability index according to Cronbach's alpha was 0.782. This high rate of reliability corroborates the validity of the research findings (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Table 5 shows the technical data for the research.

SEE TABLE 5

The data compiled were organised, tabulated and analysed using SPSS 15.0. Data processing was carried out using univariate and bivariate statistical tools and applying cluster analysis. Specifically, the study presents the analysis of the respondent's sociodemographic profile, the different aspects related to the All-Inclusive System and the cluster analysis.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 6 shows the main data items for the sociodemographic characteristics of the tourists who responded to the survey on the island of Sal.

SEE TABLE 6

From the results shown in Table 6, we conclude that the average tourist staying at a resort on Sal is a university graduate and has a medium-high income level. The proportions of visitors in three different age groups are similar. The finding that the tourists staying at the resort hotels in this island have a high level of education concurs with the conclusions drawn by Yang and Wall (2009) and by Özdemir et al. (2012). The visitors' main country of origin is the UK, followed by France, Germany and Portugal, corresponding to the nationality of the major tour operators operating in Cape Verde. Among other countries of origin, the most numerous are European, and thus we conclude that the majority of tourists visiting the island are from Europe. These results are consistent with research conducted by Anderson (2012) in

the Balearic Islands (Spain), who reported that tourists are mostly European, aged about 45 years and with an average income level. However, the income level of the tourists in the island of Sal, according to our survey, is higher than that found by Anderson (2010). We observed an association between income level and gender (Pearson chi-square coefficient: 9.223, $p=0.056$), between income and age (Pearson chi-square coefficient: 76.485, $p=0.000$) between income and education (Pearson chi-square coefficient: 98.686, $p=0.000$) and between income and country of origin (Pearson chi-square coefficient: 91.762, $p=0.000$).

On average, tourists spent one week on the island (49.9% of respondents), which is in accordance with Anderson's study (2010) of the Balearic Islands (Spain) for this type of visitor, and with that of Özdemir et al. (2012), carried out in Turkey. Most tourists travelled with a partner (51.2%) or with co-workers and/or friends (23.1%). For 75% of the tourists who responded to our questionnaire, this was their first trip to the island of Sal. Most became aware of this tourist destination through the recommendation of friends and family (26.7%) or by obtaining information from the internet (24.0%). 76.4% of respondents had previously taken a holiday using the all-inclusive system, which corroborates the conclusion reached by Anderson (2010).

Table 7 shows the tourists' opinions presented on a 5-point Likert scale (from 1, strongly disagree, to 5, strongly agree), regarding various issues related to the AIS.

SEE TABLE 7

Table 7 shows that most tourists agree with the statement that the AIS allows them to know exactly what they will pay for their holiday. This finding is one that Çizel et al. (2013) highlighted as a positive aspect of the AIS. However, the questionnaire respondents mostly disagree that this system, by itself, determines the quality of the tourism product supplied. The main drawback of the AIS, according to Table 7, is that under this system visitors are

encouraged not to leave the hotel and thus do not discover the real culture of the area. This finding confirms the conclusions of Gil Moreno et al. (2002) and Çiftçi et al. (2007).

With respect to visitors' opinions on the resort where they had stayed, under the AIS, we conducted a cluster analysis and identified three different groups, with a total of 508 cases among the total of 516 respondents. Cluster 1 contained 84 cases (16.55%), Cluster 2 had 168 (33.07%) and Cluster 3 had 256 (50.38%). Table 8 shows the score obtained for each of the variables related to the resort, for each cluster. Column 5 presents the corresponding F and p-values. Table 9 shows the distance between the cluster centres.

SEE TABLE 8

SEE TABLE 9

According to Table 8, all three groups of respondents rated the beaches most highly. In Group 1, apart from the beaches, the aspects that were most highly appreciated were the sports facilities and the shopping area, while the factor that scored lowest was the food provided within the resort. In Group 2, after the beaches, customer service and cleanliness within the resort itself were the aspects that were highest rated, and the lowest score corresponded to the shopping area. In Group 3, after the beaches, the most valued aspects of the resort were the cleanliness of the resort itself and the customer service provided (coinciding in this respect with Group 2). The least appreciated aspect of the resort, in this case too, was the shopping area. Both the cleanliness of the resort and the customer attention service provided were very highly appreciated, which is in line with the findings of Ördemiz et al. (2012).

In Group 2 (high satisfaction), all items obtained a score higher than 4, with the least favourable scores being given to the shopping area within the resort, and the offers made within the resort of excursions to visit the island. In Group 1 (low satisfaction), all the variables were scored in the range from 2.0 to 2.7. It is interesting to note that these

respondents gave a very low score to the food provided in the hotel and to the comfort of the rooms. Finally, in Group 3 (average satisfaction), the scores for the items ranged from 2.9 to 4.1. In this case, the lowest degree of satisfaction concerned the shopping area and the leisure activities offered within the hotel, a finding that coincides with the results reported by Özdemir et al. (2012).

The assessments made by each of the groups in relation to the three key variables for the island of Sal – the price of the holiday, the accommodation provided and the level of public safety – are presented in Table 10, using an ANOVA based on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1, very poor to 5, very good.

SEE TABLE 10

As can be seen in Table 10, of the three variables analysed for Clusters 1 and 3, the most highly valued is that of public safety, and in Cluster 2 this aspect is also appreciated, although not as highly as the question of accommodation. It has been reported elsewhere that tourists consider public safety to be a crucial element in deciding upon a holiday destination (Enright & Newton, 2004).

Table 11 shows the main characteristics of each cluster.

SEE TABLE 11

An interesting fact shown in Table 11 is that the persons who had never previously stayed at an AIS resort were least satisfied with the experience.

The visitors' overall level of satisfaction with their stay at the resort island of Sal, for each of the clusters, measured on a 5-point Likert scale (ranging from 1-very dissatisfied, to 5-very satisfied) is presented in Table 12.

SEE TABLE 12

According to Table 12, the average level of satisfaction ranged from 3.61 in Group 1 to 4.18 in Group 2. Thus, 74.8% of the tourists surveyed were satisfied or very satisfied with

their stay at the resort on the island of Sal. No association was detected between satisfaction and gender (Pearson chi-square coefficient: 4.225, $p=0.376$). On the other hand, there was an association between satisfaction and age (Pearson chi-square coefficient: 34.128, $p=0.005$), between the degree of satisfaction and education (Pearson chi-square coefficient: 16.294; $p=0.038$) and between the degree of satisfaction and the country of origin (Pearson chi-square coefficient: 58.513, $p=0.001$).

CONCLUSIONS

The considerable tourist development that has taken place in Cape Verde in recent years, together with the associated boom in the construction industry, has allowed this country to achieve strong economic growth. This development has arisen by two different processes: on the one hand, through the creation of large AIS resorts, mainly on the islands of Sal and Boa Vista and funded by foreign capital, especially European capital; on the other hand, through the creation of small hotels and businesses that provide tourism-related services in the other islands. These concerns are mainly financed with local capital, some of which is derived from emigrants' remittances.

This paper presents a study of the main economic indicators of Cape Verde for the time period 2004-2013, during which significant development took place, due in part to strong growth in the tourist industry.

We also analyse tourism demand with respect to the AIS applied on the island of Sal, the main resort island of Cape Verde, using a cluster analysis. The main finding is that the aspect of the resort hotel that tourists most highly appreciate is the quality of the nearby beaches. Other areas that are highly rated include the cleanliness of the resort and the customer attention provided. The main element considered in need of improvement is that of the shopping area located within the hotel.

As a practical application of our findings, we believe consideration of these results could be very useful for public managers working in the planning and promotion of tourism and for private companies in this field.

The main limitation of this study is the time period during which the fieldwork was conducted, since (and taking into account that Cape Verde is unaffected by seasonality) the research should be strengthened by fieldwork conducted in other months to determine whether tourists' opinions vary according to the time of their visit.

As a line for future research, we intend to analyse the trade relations between the resorts and local businesses, and the potential of these business relationships.

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Table 1 shows the main economic indicators of the country for the time period studied, i.e., from 2004 to 2013.

Table 1. Main economic indicators: 2004-2013

	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Real growth rate of GDP (%)	10.2	6.9	8.0	15.2	6.7	2.2	3.7	4.5	2.4	0.5
Unemployment rate (%)	n. a.	n. a.	13.4	15.2	13.0	13.1	10.7	12.2	16.8	16.4
Inflation (%)	-1.9	0.4	4.8	4.4	6.8	1	2.1	4.5	2.5	1.5
Gross tourism receipts (% of GDP)	9.4	10.7	16.1	19.3	19.5	16.6	16.7	20.9	23.6	25.2
Income from tourism (millions of dollars)	153	177	286	426	542	249	270	342	414	431
Migrants' remittances (% of GDP)	9.9	12.2	10.6	8.8	8.2	7.5	7.5	9.5	9.5	9.1
Foreign direct investment (% of GDP)	6.6	7.5	10.6	12.6	14.7	10.2	8.3	8.1	3.2	2.0
Public deficit (% of GDP)	-0.8	-3.0	-3.3	1.2	-1.6	-5.8	-10.5	-7.7	-7.6	-7.4
Public debt (% of GDP)	86.5	87.45	80.8	71.9	73.55	80.0	80.4	87.0	85.0	92.0

Source: Own elaboration, based on data from the Central Bank of Cape Verde (2014)
n. a.: Data not available

Table 2. Numbers of tourists: 2004-2013

Year	Total tourists Cape Verde	Tourists Sal	Overnight stays Cape Verde	Overnight stays Sal
2004	184,738	129,608 (70.1%)	865,125	685,198 (79.2%)
2005	233,548	162,625 (69.6%)	935,505	709,982 (75.9%)
2006	280,582	167,222 (59.6%)	1,368,018	945,421 (69.1%)
2007	312,880	192,038 (61.3%)	1,432,746	1,101,642 (76.9%)
2008	333,354	190,137 (57.0%)	1,827,196	1,347,076 (73.7%)
2009	330,319	148,005 (44.8%)	2,021,752	1,073,300 (53.1%)
2010	381,831	154,115 (40.4%)	2,342,282	1,104,004 (47.1%)
2011	475,294	168,322 (35.4%)	2,827,562	1,214,660 (41.3%)
2012	533,877	188,175 (35.2%)	3,334,275	1,406,543 (42.2%)
2013	552,144	207,691 (37.8%)	3,436,111	1,481,980 (43.1%)

Source: Own elaboration, based on National Statistics Institute of Cape Verde (2014)

Table 3. Tourist infrastructure in Cape Verde: 2004-2013

	Hotels	Bedrooms	Beds	Staff employed
2004	108	3,150	5,804	2,165
2005	132	4,406	8,278	3,199
2006	142	4,836	8,828	3,290
2007	150	5,368	9,767	3,450
2008	158	6,172	11,420	4,081
2009	173	6,367	11,720	4,120
2010	178	5,891	11,397	4,058
2011	195	7,901	14,076	5,178
2012	207	8,522	14,999	5,385
2013	222	9,058	15,995	5,755

Source: Own elaboration, based on National Statistics Institute of Cape Verde (2014)

Table 4. Tourist infrastructure in the island of Sal: 2004-2013

	Hotels	Bedrooms	Beds	Staff employed
2004	24 (22.2%)	1,707 (54.2%)	3,409 (58.7%)	1,251 (57.8%)
2005	32 (24.2%)	2,354 (53.4%)	4,600 (55.6%)	1,721 (53.8%)
2006	34 (23.9%)	2,673 (55.3%)	5,219 (59.1%)	1,774 (53.9%)
2007	34 (22.7%)	3,028 (56.4%)	5,862 (60.0%)	2,038 (59.1%)
2008	34 (21.5%)	2,934 (47.5%)	5,838 (51.1%)	1,978 (48.5%)
2009	35 (20.2%)	2,957 (46.4%)	5,872 (50.1%)	1,922 (46.7%)
2010	27 (15.2%)	2,141 (36.3%)	5,205 (45.7%)	1,654 (40.1%)
2011	27 (13.8%)	3,059 (38.7%)	6,295 (44.7%)	2,027 (39.1%)
2012	30 (14.5%)	3,439 (40.3%)	6,917 (46.1%)	2,014 (37.4%)
2013	31 (13.9%)	3,819 (42.2%)	7,490 (46.8%)	2,467 (42.9%)

Source: Own elaboration, based on National Statistics Institute of Cape Verde (2014)

Table 5. Technical data for the research

Number of persons who visited the island of Sal (2013)	207,691
Sample	516 surveys
Sampling error	±4.31%
Format	Convenience sampling
Period of application	April-June 2014
Control of the sample	Performance and supervision of the field study by the authors

Source: Own elaboration

Table 6. Sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents

Variables		%	Variables		%
Sex (n = 516)	Male	51.0	Age (n = 516)	< 30 years	20.3
	Female	49.0		30-39 years	20.0
				40-49 years	25.8
				50-59 years	17.8
				> 59 years	16.1
Income (n = 500)	< €700	1.8	Country of origin (n = 516)	United Kingdom	21.9
	€700 - €1000	3.8		France	15.9
	€1001-€1500	21.8		Germany	15.1
	€1501 - €2500	28.4		Portugal	12.6
	> €2500	44.2		Italy	11.8
			Sweden	8.7	
			Netherlands	7.0	
			Belgium	7.0	
Education (n = 511)	Primary	2.7	First visit? (n = 516)	Yes	75.0
	Secondary	43.4		No	25.0
	University	53.9			
How did you hear of this holiday area? (n = 516)	Friends	26.7	Prior experience of AIS? (n = 516)	None	23.6
	Internet	24.0		Once	28.5
	Travel agency	18.6		Twice	12.8
	Brochure	18.6		3-5 times	14.5
	Other	12.1		> 5 times	20.6

Source: Own elaboration

Table 7. Evaluation of various aspects related to the all-inclusive system

Item	Mean
In the AIS, the services included in the price and those which are not included should be made clear to the consumer. Thus, consumers can be fully aware of extra costs that may be incurred.	3.75
Tourists who spend all their time in the hotel will not get to know the island and therefore will be unaware of the social and historical structure of the island, which is a big problem for marketing the country's attractions.	3.55
Hotels that have the financial power to apply the AIS should not lower prices and quality, because the system is not a concept that should be applied to every hotel.	3.39
The hotels that apply the AIS reduce the quality of the goods and services they supply in order to increase profits. Therefore, staff are unskilled, wages are low and the tourist experience is of ever-poorer quality.	3.28
The AIS could be unfair competition to other establishments on the island that provide a high-quality service and do not use this system.	3.28
The AIS does not encourage tourists to visit the town and go shopping. Therefore, the increase in tourist numbers does not benefit local shops. When tourism is considered as a whole, the local commerce system will inevitably consider this a disadvantage.	3.12
Tourists spend all their time in the hotel but blame any problems on the entire tourism system in the area.	2.98

Source: Own elaboration

Table 8. Assessment of the tourist-attraction variables, by clusters

	CLUSTER			F (p-value)
	1	2	3	
Beaches	2.7	4.6	4.1	162.910 (0.000)*
Sports facilities	2.7	4.4	3.1	202.063 (0.000)*
Shopping area	2.5	4.1	2.9	172.742 (0.000)*
Cleanliness	2.4	4.5	3.9	268.564 (0.000)*
Night life	2.4	4.4	3.3	211.522 (0.000)*
Excursions	2.4	4.2	3.5	192.957 (0.000)*
Leisure activities	2.3	4.5	3.1	167.351 (0.000)*
Customer attention	2.3	4.6	3.7	107.487 (0.000)*
Drinks	2.2	4.4	3.6	127.351 (0.000)*
Rooms	2.1	4.3	3.7	185.243 (0.000)*
Meals	2.0	4.5	3.6	118.304 (0.000)*

Source: Own elaboration

* Significant at 5%

Table 9. Distance between the cluster centres

Cluster	1	2	3
1		7.091	4.089
2	7.091		3.427
3	4.089	3.427	

Source: Own elaboration

Table 10. ANOVA for each of the clusters and for tourism-related variables

	CLUSTER			F (p-value)
	1	2	3	
Public safety	2.76	4.19	3.79	66.238 (0.000)*
Price of the holiday	2.70	3.63	3.32	25.065 (0.000)*
Accommodation	2.54	4.25	3.65	104.238 (0.000)*

Source: Own elaboration

* Significant at 5%

Table 11. Main characteristics of the clusters

Cluster 1 (low satisfaction)	Cluster 2 (high satisfaction)	Cluster 3 (reasonable satisfaction)
Higher percentage of men	Higher percentage of men	Higher percentage of women
Age 40-59 years	Age less than 50 years	Age 40-49 or over 60 years
University education	Secondary and university education	Secondary and university education
UK and Netherlands	UK and Germany	UK and France
High income	Medium-high income	High income
Higher percentage of persons who had never previously stayed at an AIS resort	Higher percentage of persons who had previously stayed at an AIS resort	Higher percentage of persons who had previously stayed at an AIS resort

Source: Own elaboration

Table 12. Level of satisfaction, by clusters

	CLUSTER			F (p-value)
	1	2	3	
Level of satisfaction	3.61	4.18	3.75	23.598 (0.000)*

Source: Own elaboration

* Significance < 5%

Dear editor

Clayton W. Barrows

International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration

Dear Editor,

I am writing to submit our manuscript entitled, “The All-inclusive Tourism system in Cape Verde islands: the tourists’ perspective” for consideration for publication in the International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration

In this study, we examine the tourist resort island of Sal in the Archipelago of Cape Verde where this sort of research has not been done before and it presents the results of a study focused on tourists visiting the island under all-inclusive system. The results show tourists’ high level of satisfaction especially those aspects related to the beaches and the public safety in this emerging tourist destination. As such this paper should be of interest to a broad readership including those interested in tourism, geography or economy.

This manuscript describes an original work and is not under consideration by any other journal. All authors approved the manuscript and its submission to International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration. We have read and have abided by the statement of ethical standards for manuscripts submitted to International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration. The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Thank you for receiving our manuscript and considering it for review. We appreciate your time and look forward to your response.

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TITLE

The All-inclusive Tourism system in Cape Verde islands: the tourists' perspective

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Responses to reviewer's comments

Firstly, we want to thank the reviewer for his/her useful comments that help us to improve the quality of this paper. Following the reviewer recommendations, we introduced in the paper the following modifications:

- In 2013, there were 31 hotels establishments in the island of Sal. However, there were seven resorts offering more than 3,000 rooms in this island in the same year. Subsequently, more than the 80% of the total available rooms in this island in 2013 belong to this lodging typology.
- In this island, all these resorts had 4 or 5 stars category and they mainly belong to Portuguese, Spanish, Italian and British hotel chains.
- We did not include in the questionnaire the resorts' typology where the tourists stayed in because we considered that the quality average of the different resorts is quite similar in Sal where all the resorts have 4 or 5 stars category. Therefore, the purpose of our study was to analyse the All-Inclusive system in general in the island of Sal and not in each particular resort.
- Also, we reinforced and updated the bibliographic references used in the study.